

Where beach and sea meet: New tools applied to CRMs exploration in Ría de Vigo (NW Spain)

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RÍAS BAIXAS: A PROMISING EXPLORATION AREA

Rías Baixas, a funnel-shaped estuarine inflow system into the coastal drainage area located in NW Spain, is mainly surrounded by Variscan metamorphic and intrusive coastal outcrops (Fig. 1). Heavy mineral placer occurrences and deposits of ilmenite (Ti), zircon (Zr), cassiterite (Sn), monazite (REE) and other minerals were formed in coastal areas by weathering of these rocks. They were exploited in the XX century (Fig. 2), explored by IGME (1976 and 1978) and more recently by the EU S34i project (Ng-Dutpa et al., 2023; 2024; Fig. 3).

Figure 2: Titania S.A. exploited ilmenite at Balarés Beach (Ponteceso, Coruña) between 1941 and 1952.

Figure 3: Placer minerals in Santa Marta (A) and Vao (B) beaches. Below, aplite-pegmatite dikes and shear bands are exploration targets in the shoreline of Ría de Vigo.

FROM TRADITIONAL TO THE MOST MODERN EARTH OBSERVATION TECHNIQUES EXPLORING MINERALS IN THE SHORELINE

Critical Raw Materials (CRM) mineralisations, including Ti, Sn, Nb, Ta, Li, REEs and Au placers, pegmatite, and hydrothermal deposits are being investigated. S34i project results improve seabed mineral mapping using novel Earth Observation (EO)-based methods supporting traditional geological mapping and ore deposit studies to explore the connection between seashore and coastal areas (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Local and regional multidisciplinary exploration in Ría de Vigo. Multiscale approach: 1) from the sea using technology aboard research vessels like hyperspectral camera on customised remotely operated vehicle (ROV) and under water drone; 2) in the coast line and labs by aerial drone imagery (UAV), geological mapping, mineralogical and geochemical studies and 3) from the space with modern high-resolution satellite imagery.

MAPPING MINERALS AND IMPROVING KNOWLEDGE IN COASTAL AREAS

Ría de Vigo is a S34i project pilot site where modern high-resolution technologies have been applied to the exploration and management of CRMs in a sustainable, economic and non invasive way. This study is providing solutions (data and new methods) by selecting the most adequate EO dataset according to the desired outcome/research question (Figs. 5-7).

Figure 5: Spectral resolution (number of bands) for the satellites examined in Ría de Vigo - preferred satellites based on spectral resolution marked in green. Below left, images from different satellites from the Ría de Vigo coastal area (a) WorldView-2, (b) Kompsat-3, (c) Sentinel-2, (d) Landsat-8. Below right, Spectral signatures of heavy minerals at the Ría de Vigo. Comparison with WorldView-3 spectral channels.

Key References:
 - IGME (1976). Investigación minera preliminar de la plataforma continental de la costa gallega.
 - IGME (1978). Investigación minera de detalle en los fondos submarinos de la zona de las Rías de Pontevedra y Vigo (GAL-RIAS).
 - Ng-Dutpa et al. (2023). Titanium, Zirconium and Rare Earth Element placer deposits in coastal environments of Rías Baixas (Galicia, NW Spain).
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 - Ng-Dutpa et al. (2024). Earth observation approach to understand coastal morphology, shoreline dynamics, and their relationship with mineral placer deposits: the case of Santa Marta Beach (Ría de Vigo, NW Spain)

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Figure 6: Geological and structural mapping using PND4 (A) and UAV (B) survey of Santa Marta Beach (Ría de Vigo). Detailed features distinguishing rock outcrops, dykes (5-45 cm wide) and veins (<5 cm wide) in zone 1; beach geomorphology and surface placer occurrence with ephemeral stream (rich in heavy minerals) in area 2. UAV surveys offer the best performance in identifying recent surface placer occurrences in coastal areas.

Figure 7: Surface and subsail exploration in Ría de Vigo show the abundance of heavy minerals in the fine sand fraction (up to 46%). Almandine, ilmenite, zircon, cassiterite and others enriched in CRMs like Zr, Nb, Hf, Ta and REEs are distributed in beaches and shallow waters. Underwater hyperspectral data provide valuable information for seafloor environmental and ecosystem studies. Heavy mineral accumulation in ripples due to tidal action.